

Cone 2- Metric Spaces and Fixed Point Theorems for Pair of Contractive Maps

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Abstract:

We review, generalize and prove some fixed point theorems for contractive maps in cone 2- metric spaces.

Key Words: Fixed point; Cone 2- metric space; Contractive mapping; Ordered Banach space.

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1. Introduction and Preliminary Notes

Fixed point theory is one of the most dynamic research subjects in nonlinear analysis. The theory itself is a beautiful mixture of analysis, topology and geometry. Over the last years or so the theory of fixed points has been revealed as a very powerful and important tool in the study of non-linear phenomena. In this area, the first important and significant result was proved by Banach [1] in 1922 for a contraction mapping in a complete metric space. The well known Banach contraction Theorems may be stated as follows:

“Every contraction mapping of a complete metric space in X into itself has a unique fixed point.”

Since then, this principle has been extended and generalized in several ways either by using the contractive condition or by imposing some additional conditions on an ambient space. This principle is one of the cornerstones in the development of fixed point theory. From inspiration of this work, several mathematicians heavily studied this field.

Motivated by this work, several authors introduced similar concepts and proved analogous fixed point theorem in 2- metric and 2- Banach space. Gahler ([2], [3], and [4]) investigated the concept of 2- metric space and give the definition as follows:

Definition 1.1: Let X be a non-empty set and let $d: X \times X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ i.e. $d: X^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfying the following conditions:

- (i) $d(x, y, x) = 0$ only if at least two x, y, z are equal.
- (ii) $d(x, y, z) = d(p(x, y, z))$ for all $x, y, z \in X$ and for all permutation $p(x, y, z)$ of x, y, z .

$$(iii) \quad d(x, y, z) \leq d(x, y, w) + d(x, w, z) + d(w, y, z)$$

for all $x, y, z, w \in X$. Then d is called a 2-metric on X and (X, d) is called a 2-metric space which will sometimes be denoted simply by X , when there is no confusion. It can be easily seen that d is a non-negative function.

Perhaps Iseki [5-7] obtained for the first time basic results on fixed point of operators in 2- metric space and in 2- Banach space. After the work of Iseki, several authors extended and generalized fixed point theorems in 2- metric and 2- Banach spaces for different types of operators of contractive type.

Recently, In 2007, Haung and Zhang[8] introduced the concept of cone metric space by generalized the concept of metric space, replacing the set of real numbers, by an ordered Banach space and obtained some fixed point theorems for mapping satisfying different contractive conditions. Subsequently, many authors have studied the strong convergence to a fixed point with contractive constant in cone metric space, see for instance [9],[10],[11],[12][13], [14]. On the other hand, B. Singh, S. Jain, and P. Bhagat [15] introduced cone 2-metric space by replacing real number in 2- metric space by an ordered Banach space and some fixed point theorem for contractive mappings on complete cone2- metric space with assumption of normality on the cone.

The purpose of this paper is to extend and improves the fixed point theorems of B. Singh, S. Jain, and P. Bhagat [15] .

First, we recall some standard notations and definitions in cone 2- metric spaces with some of their properties [15].

Definition 1.1 [15]: Let E be a real Banach space and $P \subset E$. Then P is called a cone if and only if:

- (i) P is closed, non – empty and $P \neq \{0\}$,
- (ii) $ax + by \in P$ for all $x, y \in P$ and non – negative real number a, b ;
- (iii) $x \in P$ and $-x \in P \Rightarrow x = 0 \Leftrightarrow P \cap (-P) = \{0\}$.

Given a cone $P \subset E$, we define a partial ordering \leq on E with respect to P , by $x \leq y$ if and only if $y - x \in P$. We shall write $x \ll y$ if $y - x \in \text{int } P$, $\text{int } P$ denotes the interior of P .

The cone is called normal if there exists a number $K > 0$ such that

$$x \leq y \text{ Implies } \|x\| \leq K\|y\| \text{ for all } x, y \in P.$$

The least number satisfying above is called the normal constant of P . The cone P is called regular if every non decreasing sequence in p , which is bounded from above is convergent. That is, if $\{x_n\}$ is sequence such that

$$x_1 \leq x_2 \leq \cdots \leq x_n \leq \cdots \leq y$$

For some y in E , there exist $x \in P$ such that $\|x_n - x\| \rightarrow 0 (n \rightarrow \infty)$ equivalently the cone P is regular if and only if every decreasing sequence in p , which is bounded from below is convergent. It can be easily proved that a regular cones a normal cone.

Remark 1.2[16]: If E is a real Banach space with cone P and if $a \leq \lambda a$ where $a \in P$ and $0 < \lambda < 1$, then $a = 0$.

Definition 1.3 [15]: Let X be a non-empty set. Suppose the mapping $d: X \times X \times X \rightarrow E$ i.e. $d: X^3 \rightarrow E$ satisfying the following conditions:

1. $0 \leq d(x, y, x)$, for all $x, y, z \in X$ and $d(x, y, x) = 0$ if and only if at least two x, y, z are equal.
2. $d(x, y, z) = d(p(x, y, z))$ for all $x, y, z \in X$

and for all permutation $p(x, y, z)$ of x, y, z .

$$3. \quad d(x, y, z) \leq d(x, y, w) + d(x, w, z) + d(w, y, z)$$

for all $x, y, z, w \in X$. Then d is called a cone 2-metric on X and (X, d) will be called cone 2-metric space. Cone 2-metric space will be called normal, if the cone P is normal cone.

Example 1.4[15]: Let $E = R^2$, $P = \{(x, y) \in E : x, y \geq 0\} \subset R^2$, $X = R$ and $d: X \times X \times X \rightarrow E$ such that $d(x, y, a) = (l^n, al)$ where $l = \min(|x - y|, |y - z|, |z - x|)$ and l and n are some fixed positive integers. Then (X, d) is a cone 2-metric space.

Definition 1.5[15]: Let (X, d) be a cone 2-metric space with respect to a cone P in a real Banach space E . $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ a sequence in X and $x \in X$. Then,

- (i) $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ converges to x whenever for every $c \in E$ with $0 \ll c$, there is a Natural number N such that $d(x_n, x, a) \ll c$ for all $n \geq N$ and for all $a \in X$. We denote this by $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = x$ or $x_n \rightarrow x$, as $n \rightarrow \infty$.
- (ii) $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is said to be a Cauchy sequence if for every $c \in E$ with $0 \ll c$, There is a Natural number N such that $d(x_n, x_m, a) \ll c$ for all $n, m \geq N$.
- (iii) (X, d) is called a complete cone 2-metric space if every Cauchy sequence in X is convergent

Lemma 1.6[15]: (1) Let (X, d) be a cone 2-metric space, P be a normal cone with normal constant K , $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ a sequence in X and $x \in X$. Then $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ converges to $x \in X$ if and only if $d(x_n, x_m, a) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for all $a \in X$.

- (2) Let (X, d) be a cone 2-metric space, P be a normal cone with normal constant K , $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ a sequence in X and $x \in X$. Then limit of $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is unique if it exist.
- (3) Let (X, d) be a cone 2-metric space, $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ be a sequence in X and $x \in X$. If $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ converges to $x \in X$, then $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is a Cauchy sequence
- (4) Let (X, d) be a cone 2-metric space, P be a normal cone with normal constant K . Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ be a sequence in X and $x \in X$. Then $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ is a Cauchy sequence if and only if $d(x_n, x_m, a) \rightarrow 0$ as $(n, m \rightarrow \infty)$, for all $a \in X$.
- (5) Let (X, d) be a cone 2-metric space, P be a normal cone with normal Constant K . Let $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ and $\{y_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ be two sequence in X , $x_n \rightarrow x, y_n \rightarrow y (n \rightarrow \infty)$. Then $d(x_n, y_n, a) \rightarrow (x, y, a) (n \rightarrow \infty)$.

Definition 1.7[15]: Let (X, d) be a cone 2-metric space. If for every sequence $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ in X , there is a subsequence $\{x_{n_k}\}_{k \geq 1}$ of $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 1}$ convergent in X . Then X is called a sequentially compact cone 2-metric space.

2. Main Results

In this section we shall prove some fixed point theorems for pair of contractive maps by using normality of the cone.

Theorem 2.1: Let (X, d) be a complete cone metric space and suppose the mapping $T_1, T_2: X \rightarrow X$ satisfy the contractive condition,

$$d(T_1x, T_2y, a) \leq \alpha d(x, y, a) + \beta d(T_1x, x, a) + \gamma d(T_2y, y, a)$$

For all $x, y, a \in X$, for some fixed $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$ with $\alpha + \beta + \gamma < 1$.

Then T_1 and T_2 have unique common fixed point in X and for any $x \in X$, the iterative sequence $\{T^{2n+1}_x\}$ and $\{T^{2n+2}_x\}$ convergent to the common fixed point.

Proof: Choose $x \in X$. Set $x_1 = T_1 x_0, x_3 = T_1 x_2 = T^3_1 x_0, \dots$

$$x_{2n+1} = T x_{2n} = T^{2n+1} x_0$$

Similarly, we have $x_2 = T_2 x_1, x_3 = T_2^2 x_0, x_4 = T_2 x_3 = T_2^4 x_0, \dots$

$$x_{2n+2} = T x_{2n+1} = T^{2n+2} x_0$$

From (2.1) Taking $x = x_{2n}$ and $y = x_{2n-1}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) &= d(T_1 x_{2n}, T_2 x_{2n-1}, a) \\ &\leq \alpha d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a) + \beta d(T_1 x_{2n}, x_{2n}, a) + \gamma d(T_2 x_{2n-1}, x_{2n-1}, a) \\ &\leq \alpha d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a) + \beta d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) + \gamma d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a) \end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$(1 - \beta) d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) \leq (\alpha + \gamma) d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a)$$

$$\Rightarrow d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) \leq \frac{(\alpha + \gamma)}{(1 - \beta)} d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a), \text{ for all } n \geq 1$$

$$d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) = L d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a),$$

$$\text{Where } L = \frac{(\alpha + \gamma)}{(1 - \beta)} \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$\leq L^2 F\{d(x_{2n-1}, x_{2n-2}, a)\}$$

$$\leq \dots \dots \dots \leq L^n F\{d(x_1, x_0, a)\} \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Also for $K > t$, we have

$$d(x_{2k} x_{2k-1}, x_{2t}) \leq L d(x_{2k-1}, x_{2k-2}, x_{2t})$$

$$\leq L^2 d(x_{2k-1}, x_{2k-2}, x_{2t})$$

$$\leq \dots \dots \dots \leq$$

$$\leq L^{2k-2t-1} d(x_{2t+1}, x_{2t}, x_{2t})$$

$$= 0 \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Now for $n > m$, with using (3) and (4), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
d(x_{2n}, x_{2m}, a) &\leq d(x_{2n}, x_{2m}, x_{2n-1}) + d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a) + d(x_{2n-1}, x_{2m}, a) \\
&\leq L^{2n-1}d(x_1, x_0, a) + d(x_{2n-1}, x_{2m}, x_{2n-2}) + d(x_{2n-1}, x_{2n-2}, a) + d(x_{2n-2}, x_{2m}, a) \\
&\leq (L^{2n-1} + L^{2n-2})d(x_1, x_0, a) + d(x_{2n-2}, x_{2m}, a) \\
&\dots\dots\dots \\
&\dots\dots\dots \\
&\leq (L^{2n-1} + L^{2n-2} + \dots \dots \dots + L^{2m+1})d(x_1, x_0, a) + d(x_{2m+1}, x_{2m}, a) \\
&\leq (L^{2n-1} + L^{2n-2} + \dots \dots \dots + L^{2m+1} + L^{2m})d(x_1, x_0, a) \\
&= L^{2m}(1 + L + L^2 + \dots \dots \dots + L^{2n-2m-1})d(x_1, x_0, a) \\
&\leq \frac{L^{2m}}{1-L} F(d(x_1, x_0, a)), \text{ as } L < 1 \text{ and } P \text{ is closed}
\end{aligned}$$

Thus we have

$$\|d(x_{2n}, x_{2m}, a)\| \leq \frac{L^m}{1-L} \|K(d(x_1, x_0, a))\|.$$

This implies that $d(x_{2n}, x_{2m}, a) \rightarrow 0$, ($n, m \rightarrow \infty$), for all $a \in X$. Hence $\{x_{2n}\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in (X, d) is a complete cone 2- metric space, there exist $x^* \in X$ such that $x_{2n} \rightarrow x^*(n \rightarrow \infty)$. i.e. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n = z$. Now for any $a \in X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
d(T_1x^*, x^*, a) &\leq d(T_1x^*, x^*, T_1x_{2n}) + d(T_1x^*, T_1x_{2n}, a) + d(T_1x_{2n}, x^*, a) \\
&\leq \alpha d(x^*, x_{2n}, x^*) + \beta d(T_1x^*, x^*, x^*) + \gamma d(T_1x_{2n}, x_{2n}, x^*) \\
&\quad + \alpha d(x^*, x_{2n}, a) + \beta d(T_1x^*, x^*, a) + \gamma d(T_1x_{2n}, x_{2n}, a) + d(x_{2n+1}, x^*, a)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - \beta)d(T_1x^*, x^*, a) \leq \alpha d(x^*, x_{2n}, a) + \gamma d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, x^*) + \gamma d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) + d(x_{2n+1}, x^*, a)$$

$$\Rightarrow d(T_1x^*, x^*, a) \leq \frac{1}{1-\beta} \{ \alpha d(x^*, x_{2n}, a) + \gamma d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, x^*) + \gamma d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) + d(x_{2n+1}, x^*, a) \}$$

On taking limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and by using Lemma 1.5(4), we obtain that

$$d(T_1x^*, x^*, a) = 0$$

This implies that $T_1x^* = x^*$. So x^* is a fixed point of T_1 . Now if y^* is another fixed point of T_1 , then

$$\begin{aligned}
d(x^*, y^*, a) &= d(T_1x^*, T_1y^*, a) \\
&\leq \alpha d(x^*, y^*, a) + \beta d(T_1x^*, x^*, a) + d(T_1y^*, y^*, a)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \alpha d(x^*, y^*, a) + \beta d(x^*, x^*, a) + d(y^*, y^*, a)$$

By using remark 1.2, we obtain that $d(x^*, y^*, a) = 0$ and $x^* = y^*$. Therefore the fixed point of T_1 is unique.

Similarly it can be established that $T_2 x^* = x^*$. Hence $T_1 x^* = x^* = T_2 x^*$. Thus x^* is common point of pair of T_1 and T_2 . This completes the proof.

On taking $\beta = \gamma = 0$ in theorem in 2.1, we get the following corollary in the setting of a cone 2- metric space

Corollary 2.2: Let (X, d) be a complete cone metric space and suppose the mapping $T_1, T_2: X \rightarrow X$ satisfy the contractive condition,

$$d(T_1 x, T_2 y, a) \leq \alpha d(x, y, a) \quad \text{for all } x, y, a \in X, \text{ for some } \alpha \in [0, 1] \text{ is a constant.}$$
 Then T_1 and T_2 have unique common fixed point in X and for any $x \in X$, the iterative sequence $\{T^{2n+1}_x\}$ and $\{T^{2n+2}_x\}$ convergent to the common fixed point.

Corollary 2.3: Let (X, d) be a complete cone metric space and suppose the mapping $T_1, T_2: X \rightarrow X$ satisfy for some positive integer n ,

$$d(T_1^{2n+1} x, T_2^{2n+2} y, a) \leq \alpha d(x, y, a) \quad \text{for all } x, y, a \in X, \text{ where } \alpha \in [0, 1] \text{ is a constant.}$$
 Then T_1 and T_2 have unique common fixed point in X and for any $x \in X$, the iterative sequence $\{T_1^{2n+1}_x\}$ and $\{T_2^{2n+2}_x\}$ convergent to the common fixed point.

Proof: In view of Corollary 2.2, T_1^{2n+1} has unique fixed point of x^* . Now $T_1^{2n+1}(T_1 x^*) = T_1(T_1^{2n+1} x^*) = (T_1 x^*)$, so $T_1 x^*$ is also a fixed point of T_1^{2n+1} . As the fixed point of T_1^{2n+1} is unique, therefore $T_1 x^* = x^*$. Thus x^* is a fixed point of T_1 .

Similarly, it can be established that $T_2 x^* = x^*$. Hence $T_1 x^* = x^* = T_2 x^*$. Thus x^* is common point of pair of T_1 and T_2 .

Corollary 2.4: Let (X, d) be a complete cone metric space and suppose the mapping $T_1, T_2: X \rightarrow X$ satisfy the contractive condition,

$$d(T_1 x, T_2 y, a) \leq \alpha [d(T_1 x, x, a) + \gamma d(T_2 y, y, a)]$$

For all $x, y, a \in X$, where $\alpha \in [0, \frac{1}{2}]$ is a constant. Then T_1 and T_2 have unique common fixed point in X and for any $x \in X$, the iterative sequence $\{T^{2n+1}_x\}$ and $\{T^{2n+2}_x\}$ convergent to the fixed point.

Proof: The proof of this corollary follows by taking $\alpha = 0$ and $\beta = \gamma = \alpha$ in theorem 2.1.

Theorem 2.5: Let (X, d) be a complete cone metric space and suppose the mapping $T_1, T_2: X \rightarrow X$ satisfy the contractive condition,

$$d(T_1 x, T_2 y, a) \leq \alpha d(x, y, a) + \beta d(T_1 x, y, a) + \gamma d(T_2 y, x, a)$$

For all $x, y, a \in X$, for some fixed $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$ with $\alpha + \beta + \gamma < 1$.

Then T_1 and T_2 have unique common fixed point in X and for any $x \in X$, the iterative sequence $\{T^{2n+1}_x\}$ and $\{T^{2n+2}_x\}$ convergent to the common fixed point.

Proof: Choose $x \in X$. Set $x_1 = T_1 x_0, x_3 = T_1 x_2 = T^3_1 x_0, \dots$

$$x_{2n+1} = T x_{2n} = T^{2n+1} x_0 \dots\dots\dots$$

Similarly, we have $x_2 = T_2 x_1, x_3 = T_2^2 x_0, x_4 = T_2 x_3 = T_2^4 x_0, \dots$

$$x_{2n+2} = T x_{2n+1} = T^{2n+2} x_0 \dots\dots\dots$$

From (2.1) Taking $x = x_{2n}$ and $y = x_{2n-1}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) &= d(T_1 x_{2n}, T_2 x_{2n-1}, a) \\ &\leq \alpha d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a) + \beta d(T_1 x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a) + \gamma d(T_2 x_{2n-1}, x_{2n}, a) \\ &\leq \alpha d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a) + \beta d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n-1}, a) + \gamma d(x_{2n}, x_{2n}, a) \\ &\leq \alpha d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a) + \beta [d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) + d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a)] \end{aligned}$$

This implies

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - \beta) d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) &\leq (\alpha + \beta) d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a) \\ \Rightarrow d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) &\leq \frac{(\alpha + \beta)}{(1 - \beta)} d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a), \text{ for all } n \geq 1 \\ d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) &= L d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a), \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Where } L = \frac{(\alpha + \beta)}{(1 - \beta)} \dots\dots\dots (2.5.2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq L^2 F\{d(x_{2n-1}, x_{2n-2}, a)\} \\ &\leq \dots\dots\dots \leq L^n F\{d(x_1, x_0, a)\} \dots\dots\dots (2.5.3) \end{aligned}$$

Also for $K > t$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} d(x_{2k} x_{2k-1}, x_{2t}) &\leq L d(x_{2k-1}, x_{2k-2}, x_{2t}) \\ &\leq L^2 d(x_{2k-1}, x_{2k-2}, x_{2t}) \\ &\leq \dots\dots\dots \leq \\ &\leq L^{2k-2t-1} d(x_{2t+1}, x_{2t}, x_{2t}) \\ &= 0 \dots\dots\dots (2.5.4) \end{aligned}$$

Now for $n > m$, with using (3) and (4), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
d(x_{2n}, x_{2m}, a) &\leq d(x_{2n}, x_{2m}, x_{2n-1}) + d(x_{2n}, x_{2n-1}, a) + d(x_{2n-1}, x_{2m}, a) \\
&\leq L^{2n-1}d(x_1, x_0, a) + d(x_{2n-1}, x_{2m}, x_{2n-2}) + d(x_{2n-2}, x_{2n-2}, a) + d(x_{2n-2}, x_{2m}, a) \\
&\leq (L^{2n-1} + L^{2n-2})d(x_1, x_0, a) + d(x_{2n-2}, x_{2m}, a) \\
&\dots\dots\dots \\
&\dots\dots\dots \\
&\leq (L^{2n-1} + L^{2n-2} + \dots \dots \dots + L^{2m+1})d(x_1, x_0, a) + d(x_{2m+1}, x_{2m}, a) \\
&\leq (L^{2n-1} + L^{2n-2} + \dots \dots \dots + L^{2m+1} + L^{2m})d(x_1, x_0, a) \\
&= L^{2m}(1 + L + L^2 + \dots \dots \dots + L^{2n-2m-1})d(x_1, x_0, a) \\
&\leq \frac{L^{2m}}{1-L}F(d(x_1, x_0, a)), \text{ as } L < 1 \text{ and } P \text{ is closed}
\end{aligned}$$

Thus we have

$$\|d(x_{2n}, x_{2m}, a)\| \leq \frac{L^m}{1-L} \|K(d(x_1, x_0, a))\|.$$

This implies that $d(x_{2n}, x_{2m}, a) \rightarrow 0$, $(n, m \rightarrow \infty)$, for all $a \in X$. Hence $\{x_{2n}\}$ is a Cauchy sequence in (X, d) is a complete cone 2- metric space, there exist $x^* \in X$ such that $x_{2n} \rightarrow x^*(n \rightarrow \infty)$. i. e. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_{2n} = z$. Now for any $a \in X$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
d(T_1x^*, x^*, a) &\leq d(T_1x^*, x^*, T_1x_{2n}) + d(T_1x^*, T_1x_{2n}, a) + d(T_1x_{2n}, x^*, a) \\
&\leq \alpha d(x^*, x_{2n}, x^*) + \beta d(T_1x^*, x_{2n}, a) + \gamma d(T_1x_{2n}, x^*, x^*) \\
&\quad + \alpha d(x^*, x_{2n}, a) + \beta d(T_1x^*, x^*, a) + \gamma d(T_1x_{2n}, x^*, a) \\
&\quad + d(x_{2n+1}, x^*, a) \dots\dots\dots \text{By (2.5.1)}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow (1 - \beta)d(T_1x^*, x^*, a) \leq \alpha d(x^*, x_{2n}, a) + \gamma d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, x^*) + \gamma d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) + d(x_{2n+1}, x^*, a)$$

$$\Rightarrow d(T_1x^*, x^*, a) \leq \frac{1}{1-\beta} \{ \alpha d(x^*, x_{2n}, a) + \gamma d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, x^*) + \gamma d(x_{2n+1}, x_{2n}, a) \} + d(x_{2n+1}, x^*, a)$$

On taking limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ and by using Lemma 1.5(4), we obtain that $d(T_1x^*, x^*, a) = 0$

This implies that $T_1x^* = x^*$. So x^* is a fixed point of T_1 . Now if y^* is another fixed point of T_1 , then

$$d(x^*, y^*, a) = d(T_1x^*, T_1y^*, a)$$

$$\leq \alpha d(x^*, y^*, a) + \beta d(T_1 x^*, x^*, a) + d(T_1 y^*, y^*, a)$$

$$\leq \alpha d(x^*, y^*, a) + \beta d(x^*, x^*, a) + d(y^*, y^*, a)$$

By using remark 1.2, we obtain that $d(x^*, y^*, a) = 0$ and $x^* = y^*$. Therefore the fixed point of T_1 is unique.

Similarly it can be established that $T_2 x^* = x^*$. Hence $T_1 x^* = x^* = T_2 x^*$. Thus x^* is common point of pair of T_1 and T_2 . This completes the proof.

Corollary 2.6: Let (X, d) be a complete cone metric space and suppose the mapping $T_1, T_2: X \rightarrow X$ satisfy the contractive condition,

$$d(T_1 x, T_2 y, a) \leq \alpha [d(T_1 x, y, a) + \gamma d(T_2 y, x, a)]$$

For all $x, y, a \in X$, where $\alpha \in [0, \frac{1}{2}]$ is a constant. Then T_1 and T_2 have unique common fixed point in X and for any $x \in X$, the iterative sequence $\{T^{2n+1}_x\}$ and $\{T^{2n+2}_x\}$ convergent to the fixed point.

Proof: The proof of this corollary follows by taking $\alpha = 0$ and $\beta = \gamma = \alpha$ in theorem 2.5.

References

- [1] Banach's.(1922), Sur les operations dans les ensembles abstraits et leur applications aux equations integrals, *fundamental mathematicae*,3(7), 133-181.
- [2] Gahler , S. (1963), 2-metricsche Raume und ihre topologische structure, *Math. Nachr.* 26,115-148.
- [3] Gahler, S.(1995), Uber die Uniformisierbarkeit 2-metricsche Raume, *Math. Nachr.* 28, 235-244.
- [4] Gahler, S. (1966), Zur geometric 2-2-metricsche Raume, *Revne Roumaine der Mathem. Pures Et Appliques*, 11, 665-667.
- [5] Iseki, K, (1975), Fixed point theorems in 2-metric spaces, *Math. Seminar Notes, Kobe Univ.*, **3** 133-136.
- [6] Iseki, K, P. L. Sharma and B. K. Sharma(1976), Contraction type mapping on 2- metric spaces, *Math Japonicae*, **21**, 67-70.
- [7] Iseki, K. (1976) , Fixed point theorems in Banach spaces, *Math. Seminar Notes, Kobe Univ.*,**2**, 11-13.
- [8] L. G. Huang, X. Zhang, Cone metric spaces and Fixed point theorems for contractive mappings J. of Math. Anal. and App., 332(2007), 1468-1476.
- [9] Rezapour, Sh. and Hambarani, R. (2008), Some notes on the paper "cone metric spaces and fixed point theorems of contractive mappings", *J. Math. Anal. Appl.* 345 719-724.
- [10] Cho, S. H. (2012), Fixed point theorems for generalized contractive mappings on cone metric space, *Int. J. Of Math. Analysis.* 6(50), 2473-2481.
- [11] Tiwari, S. K. , Dubey, R. P. and Dubey, A. K. (2013), Cone metric spaces and fixed Point Theorems for pair of generalized contractive mappings, *Int. J. Of Math. Research*, 5(1), 77- 85.
- [12] Tiwari, S. K. , Dubey, R. P. and Dubey, A. K. (2013), Common fixed point results in cone metric Spaces, *Int. J. of Math. Research*, 2(3) (2013), 352-355.
- [13] [13] Tiwari, S.K. and R. P. Dubey (2013) , An extension of the paper "some fixed point theorems for generalized contractive mappings in cone metric spaces", *Int. J. of Math.Archive*--4(12) 112- 115.

- [14] Dubey, A. K., Shukla, R , Dubey, R. P. (2013), Cone metric spaces and Fixed point results of Generalized contractive mappings, *Advances in fixed point theory*,3(3), 568-577.
- [15] Singh, B. , Jain S. and Bhagat, P. ,(2012), Cone 2- Metric space and fixed point theorem of contractive mapping52(2), 143-151.
- [16] D. Ilic, and V. Rakocevic, Quasi contraction on cone metric space, *Applied Mathematic Letters* 22(2009), 728-731.